

Selective hydrogenation of *meta*-chloronitrobenzene over skeletal Ni-C catalyst[†]

Ajit Das, Kamala Mandy Hansda and Nagendranath Mahata*

Department of Chemistry, Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University, Purulia-723 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail: nmahata@hotmail.com

Manuscript received online 10 November 2018, accepted 30 November 2018

Methane was decomposed over Raney nickel to synthesize nickel-carbon skeletal composite materials (NiC catalysts). The catalysts were applied in the hydrogenation of *meta*-chloronitrobenzene to *meta*-chloroaniline in liquid phase under 1.5 MPa hydrogen pressure at 408 K using methanol as solvent. Substrate conversion and product selectivity were assessed by chromatographic analysis of the reaction mixtures. The NiC catalysts exhibited performance much superior to the parent Raney nickel, in terms of *meta*-chloronitrobenzene conversion as well as *meta*-chloroaniline selectivity. The composite catalysts also exhibited excellent stability in multiple successive reaction runs. The catalysts were characterised by elemental analysis, X-ray diffraction and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy. Electron transfer from carbon to nickel facilitates adsorption of *meta*-chloronitrobenzene through -NO₂ group and subsequent facile hydrogenation to *meta*-chloroaniline.

Keywords: Ni catalyst, hydrogenation, *meta*-chloronitrobenzene, Ni-C composite, charge transfer.

Introduction

Hydrogenation of -NO₂ functionality to -NH₂ functionality is very important as it is frequently encountered event during organic transformation/synthesis. Halogenated aromatic amines are important value added products because they are extensively used in industries like pesticide, herbicide, pigment, pharmaceutical sector, etc. The halogenated aromatic amines can be produced through catalytic hydrogenation of halogenated nitro aromatics. Hence, catalytic selective hydrogenations of halogenated aromatic nitro compounds to corresponding halo-amines make a class of reaction with great importance. Halo-amine selectivity is a critical issue because catalytic hydrogenation of halo-nitro aromatics may result in a series of by-products¹⁻⁴. The hydrodehalogenation side reaction should be avoided^{5,6}. Also, the accumulation of hydroxyl-amines should be suppressed because they may lead to condensation products¹.

Noble metal catalysts have been reported as efficient candidates for hydrogenation of halo-nitro aromatics to corresponding halo-amines^{2,7-11}. Application of promoters has been observed to be beneficial in augmenting halo-amine selectivity⁸. However, cost of noble metal catalysts may become a serious issue. Cheap and abundant metals like Ni

can be a preferred choice over precious metals, provided acceptable catalytic activity and product selectivity is maintained^{12,13}. Filamentous carbon stabilised nickel nano particles have been reported to be efficient in the catalytic hydrogenation of *ortho*- and *para*-chloronitrobenzene to corresponding chloroanilines¹². Also, NiC composite catalyst has been reported to be a good candidate in the hydrogenation of *para*-chloronitrobenzene to *para*-chloroaniline¹⁴. NiC composite material seems to be interesting catalyst; further studies are required in this direction. NiC catalysts are prepared by controlled carbon deposition over Raney nickel; and their catalytic performance in the hydrogenation of *meta*-chloronitrobenzene is explored in this study.

Experimental

Raney nickel (RNi) catalysts were prepared from a commercial Ni-Al alloy (Ni/Al = 50/50 w/w) following standard procedure^{14,15}. Methane was decomposed in controlled way over the RNi catalysts to deposit carbon. In a typical preparation, concentrated NaOH solution was reacted with the Ni-Al alloy powder at room temperature for 3 h with continuous stirring to leach out Al; the resulting RNi catalyst was subjected to sequential washings (several times) with distilled

[†]Invited Lecture.

water followed by ethanol. Then the RNi was transferred into a fixed bed tubular reactor carefully without exposing to air and dried under nitrogen flow ($60 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$) at 353 K for 4 h. Decomposition of methane (with a space velocity of $12 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ Ni}$) was performed at 665 K in controlled manner for a particular time in order to deposit carbon over the RNi catalyst avoiding severe disintegration of the skeletal structure^{14,15}. Thus, nickel-carbon composite material (NiC catalyst) was obtained. The reactor was then cooled down to ambient temperature under N_2 flow and the NiC composite catalyst was recovered. Three NiC catalysts - NiC-4, NiC-6, and NiC-9, were synthesized by varying the time of methane decomposition reaction. The numerals in the designation of catalysts indicate the time of methane decomposition in hours.

Several physico-chemical techniques were applied to characterise the catalysts. Nickel content was determined by elemental analysis. X-Ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was conducted using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.154 \text{ nm}$). X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was performed using $\text{Mg K}\alpha$ radiation (1253.6 eV).

Hydrogenation of *meta*-chloronitrobenzene (*m*-CNB) to *meta*-chloroaniline (*m*-CAN) was carried out in a stainless steel reactor at 408 K and 1.5 MPa of H_2 , using methanol as solvent. In a typical reaction run, calculated amounts of catalyst, *m*-CNB, and solvent were taken into the reactor and purged 6 times with H_2 . The reactor was then heated to reaction temperature, 408 K, at a heating ramp of 25 K min^{-1} under about 0.15 MPa H_2 . Finally, the H_2 pressure was adjusted to 1.5 MPa and the reaction was initiated by starting stirring.

Aliquots of reaction mixture were collected periodically and analysed chromatographically to follow the progress of the reaction. Constituents of the reaction mixtures were identified by matching chromatograms of reaction mixtures with standard chromatograms. The standard chromatograms were obtained by injecting known individual compounds (*meta*-chloronitrobenzene, *meta*-chloroaniline, chlorobenzene, aniline, nitrobenzene, etc.), as well as their mixtures. Conversion of *m*-CNB and selectivity of products were calculated as follows:

Conversion of *m*-CNB (%) = $[1 - \{\text{concentration of } m\text{-CNB}/(\text{concentration of all products} + \text{concentration of } m\text{-CNB})\}] \times 100\%$.

Selectivity of product, P (%) = $(\text{concentration of P}/\text{concentration of all products}) \times 100\%$.

Results and discussion

The catalysts were examined by elemental analysis (atomic emission spectroscopy) for nickel content. The Ni amounts (wt%) in the catalysts were found as: RNi: 88.2; NiC-4: 84.9; NiC-6: 82.3; NiC-9: 79.5.

The catalysts were subjected to XPS analysis and the spectra of Ni $2p_{3/2}$ region are shown in Fig. 1. The examination of the spectra clearly reveal that surface Ni is present in metallic (Ni^0) as well as in oxidised (Ni^{2+}) states in the NiC catalysts. Interesting observation is that there is negative shift in binding energy (BE) in the NiC catalysts. This clearly indi-

Fig. 1. Ni $2p_{3/2}$ XPS spectra of the RNi and NiC catalysts.

cates charge transfer from deposited carbon to nickel^{12,14-16}. Presence of deposited carbon in the NiC catalysts is confirmed by XRD analysis (shown below)^{14,15}.

The catalysts were also characterised by XRD, and two representative spectra are shown in Fig. 2. The spectra clearly

Fig. 2. Representative XRD patterns of NiC catalysts.

reveal that nickel is present in crystalline metallic form. Diffraction peaks at 2θ values of 44.54, 51.67 and 76.13 correspond to Ni(111), Ni(200) and Ni(220), respectively^{14,15}. No peak corresponding to nickel oxide/hydroxide was observed. However, as evidenced by XPS analysis, a very small amount of oxide/hydroxide is present on the surface which is below the detection limit of XRD. Presence of carbon is indicated by the peak at 2θ value of 26.26^{14,15}.

Catalytic hydrogenation of *m*-CNB to *m*-CAN has great significance as *m*-CAN is an important value added product like other chloroanilines. The NiC catalysts were evaluated in the selective hydrogenation of *m*-CNB to *m*-CAN in liquid phase applying methanol as solvent. Preliminary reaction runs were conducted to assess the influence of agitation of reaction mixture on *m*-CNB conversion. It was observed that catalytic conversion of *m*-CNB increases with increase in agitation rate up to 1000 rpm and then becomes constant. This indicates that at lower agitation rate (< 1000 rpm) the reaction is limited by mass transfer/diffusion of the reactant(s); mass transfer/diffusion limitation is overcome at higher agitation rate (> 1000 rpm). Hence, all reaction runs were performed with agitation rate of 1200 rpm to avoid mass transfer limitation.

The comparative performance of the catalysts on *m*-CNB hydrogenation is shown in Fig. 3. The NiC catalysts exhibited better activity compared to the RNi catalyst. The RNi catalyst took 600 min to achieve complete conversion of *m*-CNB. On the other hand, times taken by the NiC catalysts for complete conversion of *m*-CNB were 275 min (NiC-4), 235 min (NiC-6) and 180 min (NiC-9). No significant hydrodechloro-

Fig. 3. Performance of the RNi and the NiC catalysts in the hydrogenation of *meta*-chloronitrobenzene. Reaction conditions: catalyst (amount containing 1 mmol Ni), methanol (100 mL), *m*-CNB (100 mmol), 408 K, 1.5 MPa H₂, 1200 rpm.

ration was observed over the NiC catalysts; *m*-CAN selectivity was above 98%, and the rest was aniline. The RNi catalyst exhibited 94% *m*-CAN selectivity with remaining 6% aniline. No noticeable intermediates were observed over either the RNi or the NiC catalysts. Better performance of the NiC catalysts compared to RNi may be explained as follows. During the synthesis of the NiC catalysts, CH₄ is decomposed over Ni under controlled manner. Decomposition product, carbon diffuses through Ni to some extent and develops cracks on its skeletal structure^{14,15}. Thus, additional active sites are created at the cracks and it is likely that the number of newly created additional sites surpass the number of sites blocked by the deposited carbon. In consequence, the NiC catalysts exhibited better performance than the RNi catalyst in terms of *m*-CNB conversion. Higher *m*-CAN selectivity over the NiC catalysts may be due to electron enrichment of Ni sites. It is clear from the XPS spectra that BE of Ni⁰ has suffered negative shift in the NiC catalysts compared to that in the RNi catalyst. This indicates charge transfer from carbon to nickel in the NiC catalysts^{12,14-16}. It is very likely that electron enriched Ni sites repel negative part i.e. Cl of *m*-CNB. As a result, adsorption through -NO₂ becomes more favourable and subsequent facile hydrogenation leads exclusively to *m*-CAN. A schematic plausible surface reaction mechanism is shown in Fig. 4.

Reuse of catalyst in successive multiple runs is an important issue in liquid phase reaction. A sustainable catalyst exhibits fairly constant performance in successive reaction runs in terms of activity and product selectivity. The NiC catalysts were evaluated in successive multiple reaction runs. All

Fig. 4. Surface reaction between *meta*-chloronitrobenzene and hydrogen.

Fig. 5. Performance of NiC-9 catalyst in successive multiple runs for the hydrogenation of *meta*-chloronitrobenzene. Reaction conditions: as described in Fig. 3.

the catalysts exhibited almost constant activity and *m*-CAN selectivity (98–99%) in several successive runs. Fig. 5 shows a typical observation. It is evident from the results that the NiC catalysts can be reused successfully in successive multiple reaction runs.

Conclusions

NiC composite catalysts have been prepared utilising decomposition of methane to carbon and H₂ over skeletal Raney nickel.

The NiC catalysts exhibited excellent performance, superior to the parent Raney nickel, in the hydrogenation of *meta*-chloronitrobenzene to *meta*-chloroaniline.

Cracks developed in the skeletal structure by the diffused carbon accounts for the additional active sites; thereby superior activity of the NiC catalysts. On the other hand, charge transfer from deposited carbon to nickel is accounted for superior selectivity.

Acknowledgements

Ajit Das gratefully thanks Council of Scientific and Indus-

trial Research (CSIR), New Delhi for a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. M. Studer, S. Neto and H.-U. Blaser, *Top. Catal.*, 2000, **13**, 205.
2. V. Kratky, M. Kralik, M. Mearova, M. Stolcova, L. Zalibera and M. Hronec, *Appl. Catal. A: General*, 2002, **235**, 225.
3. J. Song, Z.-F. Huang, L. Pan, K. Li, X. Zhang, L. Wang and J.-J. Zou, *Appl. Catal. B: Environmental*, 2018, **227**, 386.
4. F. Cárdenas-Lizana, S. Gómez-Quero and M. A. Keane, *Appl. Catal. A: General*, 2008, **334**, 199.
5. B. Chen, U. Dingerdissen, J. G. E. Krauter, H. G. J. Lansink Rotgerink, K. Möbus, D. J. Ostgard, P. Panster, T. H. Riermeier, S. Seebald, T. Tacke and H. Trauthwein, *Appl. Catal. A: General*, 2005, **280**, 17.
6. D.-S. Lee and Y.-W. Chen, *Chinese J. Catal.*, 2013, **34**, 2018.
7. M. Zielinski, M. Pietrowski, A. Kiderys, M. Kot and E. Alwin, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 2017, **195**, 18.
8. N. Mahata, O. S. G. P. Soares, I. Rodríguez-Ramos, M. F. R. Pereira, J. J. M. Órfão and J. L. Figueiredo, *Appl. Catal. A: General*, 2013, **464-465**, 28.
9. X. Xu, X. Li, H. Gu, Z. Huang and X. Yan, *Appl. Catal. A: General*, 2012, **429-430**, 17.
10. A. Das, R. Mukherjee, R. Mandal, K. M. Hansda and N. Mahata, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2018, **95**, 1015.
11. B. Coq and F. Figueras, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **178-180**, 1753.
12. N. Mahata, A. F. Cunha, J. J. M. Orfao and J. L. Figueiredo, *Catal. Comm.*, 2009, **10**, 1203.
13. T. Fu, P. Hu, T. Wang, Z. Dong, N. Xue, L. Peng, X. Guo and W. Ding, *Chinese J. Catal.*, 2015, **36**, 2030.
14. N. Mahata, A. F. Cunha, J. J. M. Orfao and J. L. Figueiredo, *ChemCatChem*, 2010, **2**, 330.
15. N. Mahata, A. F. Cunha, J. J. M. Orfao and J. L. Figueiredo, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2012, **188**, 155.
16. N. Mahata, A. F. Cunha, J. J. M. Orfao and J. L. Figueiredo, *Appl. Catal. A: General*, 2008, **351**, 204.